

ALGAESOL

Sustainable aviation and shipping fuels from microalgae and direct solar BES technologies

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Duration: 36 months

= Deliverable: D6.1 = Initial communication kit

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Classified R-UE/EU-R	EU RESTRICTED under the Commission Decision No2015/444	
Classified C-UE/EU-C	EU CONFIDENTIAL under the Commission Decision No2015/444	

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Document version	Date	Change
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V0.2	05/09/2024	All designs finalized and incorporated, website coding finalized
V1.0	06/09/2024	Final Version

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Reviewers	Validation date
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Date	Issue	Recipients
06/08/2024	V0.1	PM, Project Coordinator
05/09/2024	V1.0	EC, Project Partners

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Executive summary

The ALGAESOL communication kit has been developed in order to increase public awareness of the ALGAESOL project and the potential of new technologies for the production of sustainable aviation fuels. This deliverable shows the initial communication materials that have been developed, the project factsheet, project flyer/leaflet and the project website.

The content of the ALGAESOL website, www.algaesol.eu, is public and the project information has been online since August 2024. The website will be actively maintained and updated throughout the project.

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1. Introduction

The deliverable D6.1 is associated with task T6.1 – “Dissemination and Communication activities”. The objective of this task is to ensure that the results of the project will be disseminated to the European research and industrial community, will target all important stakeholders, and will assure an ongoing communication flow between the general public, scientific community, technicians, experts, media, policymakers, industries, and end-users.

The task also includes the creation of a dedicated website for the project, presenting comprehensive information about the project in a visual and interactive way. This public website was created at the beginning of the project (operational since August 2024) and will be actively maintained and updated during the whole implementation of the project.

The creation of a set of promotional materials is also planned, from which, several are already included in this communication kit. Moreover, additional online and offline materials are previewed to be created, depicting the results generated in the project or on demand. Finally, social media channels are also a key tool to reach a broad audience (ALGAESOL LinkedIn profile active since July 2024) and this document presents a set of templates to be used.

Overall, all dissemination and communication efforts should follow the brand identity guideline, based on the ALGAESOL logo set, fonts and colors associated to the project, all described in Annex I of this document.

2. ALGAESOL Logo Set

Ahead of the kick off meeting of the project, which took place in Bergen, Norway on 2nd – 3rd July 2024, a consortium-wide poll was conducted to select a favourite logo from four variations designed by AMI, resulting in a clear winner. The winning design was then presented to the partners in a logo set, containing various sizes, colours and formats (.pdf, .svg, .png, .jpg).

Figure 1: ALGAESOL logo options

Figure 2: Final Logo Design

2.1. ALGAESOL Brand Identity

The ALGAESOL logo set, was a base for the visual or brand identity for the project. This visual or brand identity was inspired by the use of algae (dark green color) for sustainable aviation and shipping fuels (orange drop) and its goal is to create a unification link between all the communication and dissemination channels and efforts in the project. In Annex I, the brand identity guideline that was shared with the partners is shown.

3. ALGAESOL Website

The domain <https://algaesol.eu/> was purchased for use by the project ALGAESOL, also enabling the creation of subdomains. The website has been designed based on the visual identity of the project in the open-source software WordPress, which will enable a quick and efficient management of publications and edits. WordPress is an ideal tool to be used as content management system, as it is fully customizable and includes a variety of functional plugins (e.g. pop-up creation, registration forms or polls). This allows for fast and reliable customization and a user-friendly back-end environment, accelerating any potential request for updates and modifications. All individual pages of the website include a header with the project logo and a navigation menu allowing for quick access to any part of the website and all other communication channels of the project, as well as a footer with contact information, recognition of EU funding. Below, screenshots of the website contents are shown:

Figure 3: A screenshot of the homepage of the ALGAESOL website

The homepage is designed to briefly introduce the main innovations of ALGAESOL highlighting the project's potential for impact and the abilities of the consortium to achieve it. Furthermore, the most recent project news, such as events, interviews, conferences, etc. will also be featured on the home page, giving an instantaneous insight into the progress of the project.

Figure 4: Screenshot of the About page of the ALGAESOL website

The website includes information on the project’s mission and main objectives, developed technologies, and the expected impact. It also gives information about the partners, their expertise, and their role in the project. All media materials, results, and publications will be also referenced on the website and available for download.

Figure 5: Screenshot of the Consortium page of the ALGAESOL website

Additionally, the website encourages the users to sign-up for a dedicated newsletter. This will enable the creation of a useful contact database to share project news and updates, creating a pool of potential users or early adopters of the technology.

Finally, the contact section also allows all interested parties to contact the Project Manager and Project Coordinator and get more insight into the project activities or to establish potential cooperation.

3.1. Further Development of the ALGAESOL Website

Additional information will be published throughout the lifetime of the project, as mentioned above. Beyond the regular updates and publication of news and results, further optimization of the website and its content will ensure improved ranking on the search engine results pages for relevant keywords and thus improving the quality and quantity of website traffic.

4. Social Media Channels

Templates for social media content have been created along with the visual identity of the LinkedIn account (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/algaesol-eu/>). More details on how this content will be used will be shared in the *D6.2 Dissemination and communication plan - V1*, due on M6 of the project (October 2024).

Figure 6: LinkedIn profile

Figure 7: ALGAESOL Social Media Post Template

5. Other Dissemination Materials

Apart from the project website, two other dissemination materials have been developed, a project factsheet and a project flyer.

5.1. ALGAESOL Factsheet

The project fact sheet consists of two pages and summarizes the most important messages of the project for a scientific and professional audience.

Horizon Europe project fact sheet

ALGAESOL

PROJECT AMBITION

Develop **cost-effective, sustainable and renewable aviation and shipping fuels** based on **game-changing microalgae and direct solar fuel production and purification technologies** in order to accelerate the replacement of fossil-based energy technologies.

PROJECT DESCRIPTION

Climate change imposes challenges to energy security due to, between other reasons, resource depletion. Thus, the need for alternative energy sources is rising and ALGAESOL focus on **improving the conversion efficiency of solar energy, carbon dioxide (CO₂) and organic wastes into renewable methanol (CH₃OH), methane (CH₄) and biooils**. The project will significantly contribute to the current state-of-the-art in several aspects, such as:

Direct solar conversion bioelectrochemical system (BES) technology

- by developing and improving cutting-edge BES using a zero-waste approach;

Figure 1 Schematic overview of the ALGAESOL project concept.

Sustainable aviation and shipping fuels from microalgae and direct solar BES technologies

PROJECT FACTS

Start date: 01/05/2024

End date: 30/04/2027

Duration: 36 months

Project budget: € 3.9 M

HORIZON Research and Innovation Action (RIA)

Grant agreement: 101147112

Call: HORIZON-CL5-2023-D3-02

Topic: HORIZON-CL5-2023-D3-02-08

Keywords: Bioenergy, Microalgae, Biofuel, Fuel Production & Distribution, Sustainable transport, Photosynthetic bio-conversion, Bio-electrochemical technologies, Aviation, Shipping, Circularity, Sustainability.

Microalgae-based renewable fuel technologies

- increasing biooil (microalgal lipids) production through improvements in microalgal pathways or photosynthetic bioconversion (bioelectrochemical technology, improved algal strains, cultivation protocols, harvesting and lipid extraction);

Purification and fuel development

- by **improving purification yield** and quality of biofuels from algal lipids;

Simulations, sustainability and scale-up strategies

- employing novel simulation approaches and sustainability assessments to **ensure enhanced sustainability** (environmental, economic, social) of the developed fuels and market penetration.

EXPECTED IMPACT

- Reduce aviation and shipping biofuel production costs up to 25%, and accelerate the replacement of fossil-based energy technologies.
- Enhanced sustainability of the developed fuels by using **waste streams**, as about 80% of residual biomass generated in the value chain will be reused as input in the conversion process.
- Reduction of the **environmental impact** of biofuel production by up to 20% compared to current state-of-the-art (SoTA) processes.

CONSORTIUM

NORCE	NO
LEITAT	ES
USG	ES
DTI	DK
SIMTECH	AT
SOCAR	TR
AMI	CZ

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Funded by the European Union

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Figure 8: ALGAESOL Factsheet

5.2. ALGAESOL Flyer

The project flyer (or leaflet) gives a short overview of key objectives and activities and will be used to communicate the main messages to a wider audience.

Figure 9: ALGAESOL Flyer

5.3. ALGAESOL PowerPoint Template

The project PowerPoint template includes several layout options, to be used by all partners at internal meetings, as well as for external presentations at conferences and other dissemination events.

Figure 10: ALGAESOL PowerPoint Template

6. Conclusions

The ALGASEOL logo was selected in a consortium-wide poll and the resulting logo set served as a base for the visual identity of the project.

As the next step, ALGAESOL project website <https://algaesol.eu/> was set up, as well as the LinkedIn profile (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/algaesol-eu/>). Both channels will continue to be improved and regularly updated, with the main objective of increasing public awareness about the ALGAESOL project and the potential of using biofuels in the shipping and aviation industries. They will be also used to disseminate the project's results. The website includes all essential information about the project, as well as news, public deliverables and project outcomes and publications.

Other communication materials – namely PowerPoint template, factsheet and leaflet – were created in line with the visual identity and are previewed to be used to advertise the project to wider audiences on industrial fairs and meetings, as well as at conferences and other scientific events with the aim to establish initial interest and contact with a range of stakeholders.

7. Dissemination level

The deliverable D6.1 is Public (PU).

8. Annex I - Brand Identity Guideline

MAIN LOGO | The primary emblem of the project

LOGO VARIATION | Designed for use in varied applications

LOGO VARIATION

Designed for use in varied applications

FULL PROJECT NAME

SUSTAINABLE AVIATION AND SHIPPING FUELS FROM MICROALGAE & DIRECT SOLAR BES TECHNOLOGIES

FONTS

Font Family: Poppins
<https://fonts.google.com/specimen/Poppins>

COLOR PALETTE

R 32
G 111
B 40

#206F28

R 56
G 146
B 57

#389239

R 243
G 113
B 33

#f37121

R 246
G 141
B 61

#f68d3d

R 194
G 162
B 108

#c2a26c

R 255
G 212
B 142

#ffd48e

R 246
G 141
B 61

#f68d3d